

WHAT ABOUT...

The game?

Meet your team!

Your team is taking part in a gameshow to win money for Open Science, which has been underfunded. Meet your team and let the host know what your team name is!

Phase 1: Guess the topic for discussion and win BOBs!

To get to the juicy part, you'll need to figure out what topic you're discussing. Each team will take turns to spin the wheel for BOBs (Bogus Open Science Bucks) and guess a letter they think the phrase on the board contains. The team receives the spun amount for each letter available in the phrase. If the letter does not appear, the team wins nothing and the next team spins.

Example: if you spin 500, you guess the letter E, and there are 3 e's in 'What About Open Science?', you get 1500 in your kitty.

The next team goes. They spin, guess, get Bobs and so on until a team can guess the phrase. Guessing the entire phrase can only be done when it is their turn.

If a team lands on 'Cuts', that team's budget is cut in half...just like real life.

Phase 2: Discuss the topic and what it means for your team!

Once the phrase has been guessed, potentially provocative statements will be displayed on screen to help the teams discuss the topic.

Each team will be given an info pack. This pack provides basic information on what the topic is, a list of potential actions that can be taken in support of this topic, and cards that say 'Action', 'Resources' and 'Consensus'. In addition to the info pack, you can also use your device to look up any terms or topics you're unfamiliar with.

Based on the discussions, teams need to decide if they feel actions and/or resources should be used in support of this topic. You might wanna take some notes about what you guys have discussed.

Use the 'Action', 'Resources' and 'Consensus' cards to help remember what your team has talked about. You can also use your whiteboard marker on the laminated cards to help jog your memory.

Phase 1-2 are repeated for several rounds, depending on how many topics you're discussing.

Phase 3: Spend your BOBs!

After the last discussion round, it's time to decide how to spend your hard earned BOBs. What are you going to do to stimulate Open Science practices in your institution?

B

Using the Menu Card, which has suggested actions priced - pick what your institution will spend the BOBs that you have in your kitty on. Have your decisions changed from the initial discussion? Has the reality of pricing ruined your ambitions? Or maybe you have other plans? Tell us about it in the discussion that follows.

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1.

YOUR TEAM NAME

Your institution has sent your team to participate in "What About Open Science" gameshow. Choose your team name and introduce yourselves!

2.

G U E S S T H E
P H R A S E

Unveil the topic you'll be discussing! Guess the topic, letter by letter, and earn BOBs (Bogus Open Science Bucks) while doing so as you spin the BOBs wheel to see how much each letter is worth!

3.

Info pack

Once the topic has been guessed, your team will explore the information pack to prepare for a discussion!*

4.

Discuss!

Using the statements from the slides, discuss the topic within your team - what do you think your institution would say about this topic? Would you be willing to fight for it?

5.

Voting time!
(optional)

(This part is optional) Use the yes/no cards to indicate what your team thinks about the topic. Would you take action on this? Do you all agree about its importance? Do you think your institution has resources to support this?

6.

REPEAT

Repeat steps 2 to 4 or 5 for several topics, the host will guide you here depending on the time spent on each topic!

7.

Choose what to fund...

... or make your own suggestions

Decision time! Use the Menu Card to decide what to spend your hard earned BOBs on! You can also make your own suggestions, just remember to price it appropriately, how many BOBs would your suggestion need?

8.

Discuss your decisions with the other teams

Share your decisions with the host and the other teams. If time, you can have a wider discussion here. We hope you're inspired to bring the decisions back to your own institutions and organisations!

*The info pack contains a brief overview of the topic. You can use your phone or device to look up any information you're unfamiliar with!